

Effect of temperature on volumetric, ultrasonic and conductance behaviour of Metformin hydrochloride (MH) in water and aqueous glucose

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Abstract : The behaviour of Metformin hydrochloride (MH) in water and aqueous glucose solutions was studied to explore molecular interactions at different temperatures. The volumetric, ultrasonic and conductance studies were used for investigating the interactions of drug Metformin hydrochloride in water and aqueous glucose system. The density (ρ), ultrasonic velocity (u) and molar conductance of metformin hydrochloride in water and in (2%, 4% and 6%) aqueous solutions of glucose have been measured at (305.15, 310.15 and 315.15 K) temperatures. The density data was analysed with the help of Masson's equation. The positive value of (Φ_v^0) for MH indicates solute-solvent interactions. The solute-solute interactions were determined from Masson's coefficient (S_v), in water-glucose system at different temperatures. The ultrasonic velocity data of MH in water and water-glucose system were used to determine adiabatic compressibility (β), intermolecular free length (L_f), and specific acoustic impedance (Z). The structure making/breaking behaviour of MH in water and water-glucose system was determined on the basis of Hepler's equation and Walden's product.

Keywords : Partial molar volume, adiabatic compressibility, intermolecular free length, Walden product.

Introduction

The physicochemical interactions between a drug and functionally important molecules in a living organism may include ionic, covalent, charge transfer, hydrogen bonding, ion-dipole interactions, or hydrophobic hydration and are of great benefit to understand the pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics¹⁻³ of drugs. The studies on the physicochemical interactions in the aqueous phase through the volumetric and ultrasonic methods provide useful information in pharmaceutical^{4,5} and medicinal chemistry. The drug-water molecular interactions and their temperature dependence play an important role in understanding drug action^{6,7} at the molecular level. Such results are also helpful for predicting the absorption of drugs, transport of drugs across biological membranes, and investigating the presence, migration, and transformation of the drugs in the environment⁸⁻¹⁰. To understand the action of drugs in aqueous solution has been a subject of research as they exert their activity by interactions with biological

membrane. Drug action, i.e. drug reaching the blood stream, its extent of distribution, its binding to the receptors, and finally producing physiological action, all depend on various physicochemical properties mainly detected by various interactions^{11,12}. A knowledge of the use of drugs involving physiological and biochemical effects and their mechanism of action at macromolecular/subcellular/organ system levels can be studied in pharmacokinetics^{13,14}. All pharmacokinetic processes involve transport of drugs across biological membranes which can be well understood by transport property measurements, viz. ultrasonic speed, viscosity, diffusion, and thermal conductivity. The energy in our body comes from the food we eat. Our bodies digest the food we eat by mixing it with fluids (acids and enzymes) in the stomach. When the stomach digests food, the carbohydrate (sugars and starches) in the food breaks down into another type of sugar, called glucose¹⁵. D-Glucose is a monosaccharide from carbohydrate class, and other saccharides are part of some physiological

processes and have a key role in the structure of biological molecules¹⁶. D-Glucose occurs widely in nature and it acts as a universal substrate for the production of cellular energy in living organisms. The stomach and small intestine absorb the glucose and then release it into the bloodstream. Once in the bloodstream glucose is transported from the intestine or liver to body cells via the bloodstream, and is made available for cell absorption via the hormone insulin, produced by the body primarily in the pancreas. The blood sugar concentration or blood glucose level is the amount of glucose (sugar) present in the blood of a human or animal. When the body is working as it should, it can keep blood sugar at a normal level, which is between 70 and 120 milligrams per decilitre. However, even in people without diabetes, blood sugar levels can go up as high as 180 during or right after a meal. Within two hours after eating, blood sugar levels should drop to under 140. After several hours without eating, blood sugar can drop as low as 70. Our bodies need insulin in order to use or store glucose for energy. Without insulin, glucose stays in the bloodstream, keeping blood sugar levels high. When insulin is released from the pancreas, it travels through the bloodstream to the body's cells and tells the cell doors to open up to let the glucose in¹⁷. As glucose moves from the bloodstream into the cells, blood sugar levels start to drop. The beta cells in the pancreas can tell this is happening, so they slow down the amount of insulin they're making. At the same time, the pancreas slows down the amount of insulin that it's releasing into the bloodstream. When this happens, the amount of glucose going into the cells also slows down¹⁸. If pancreas does not secrete proper insulin to reduce glucose in the body then problem known as Diabetes occurs.

Metformin hydrochloride (MH), a white crystalline powder, has a molecular formula of (C₄H₁₁N₅HCl). It is an antidiabetic and antihyperglycemic agent^{19,20} that lowers both basal- and postprandial-elevated blood glucose in patients with non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (Type-2 diabetes), where hyperglycemia cannot be satisfactorily managed by diet alone. It is frequently referred to as

an "insulin sensitizer" because in settings of insulin resistance and hyperinsulinemia, it lowers circulating insulin levels. Recent studies show that Metformin can reduce cancer risk and/or improve cancer prognosis^{21,22}.

The study is also important whether the Metformin hydrochloride will be safer for the patient suffering from hypertension i.e. high blood pressure. If the drug behaviour is structure maker in water-glucose system then free water molecules will be less available for the solvation of sodium ions present in the blood stream and thus the medicine will be safer for the patient suffering from high blood pressure. If the drug act as structure breaker in any studied system containing water then the drug will not be safe due to high solvation of sodium ions present in the blood.

The main focus in the present paper is to study the interactions of antidiabetic drug Metformin hydrochloride (MH) in water and water-glucose systems (2%, 4% and 6% aqueous glucose) at 305.15 K, 310.15 K and 315.15 K. A change in temperature or concentration significantly affects the charge distribution in molecules, which also influence the different type of molecular interactions (H-bonding, ion-dipole and dipole-dipole etc.)²³. The present study include the molecular interactions of MH in different concentrations of glucose at different temperatures. Over the years, we are aware of the fact that volumetric data often lead to interpretations in terms of molecular interactions with in the system. Recent literature on the volumetric properties of drugs and other materials of biological importance show increasing interest in this area of research²⁴⁻²⁶.

Experimental

Materials :

1,1-Dimethylbiguanide hydrochloride, molecular formula : C₄H₁₁N₅HCl, molecular weight : 165.62 g/mol (CAS : 24390-14-5; Alfa Aesar, mass fraction ≥ 98.0%) and analytical grade, D-glucose, C₆H₁₂O₆ (CAS : 69-65-8; SD Fine Chemical, Mumbai, mass fraction ≥ 98.0%) and analytical grade was used for the investigation of the effect of temperature and concentration of MH in aqueous glucose solutions. These chemicals were used as such without any fur-

Table 1. Specification of chemicals

Chemical name	Molecular mass	Provenance	Mass fraction purity	CAS No.
Metformin hydrochloride	165.62	Alfa Aesar	≥ 98 %	24390-14-5
Glucose	180	SD Fine Chem., India	≥ 98 %	69-65-8

ther purification. Both these chemicals were vacuum dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 in desiccator for 48 h. The specifications of the chemicals used in this study are given in Table 1.

Metformin hydrochloride

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of Metformin hydrochloride.**Fig. 2.** chemical structure of glucose.

Methods :

Triply distilled and deionised water with specific conductance less than 10^{-6} Scm^{-1} was used for the preparation of solutions. Three different concentrations of glucose (2%, 4% and 6%) were used as solvent to prepare ternary solutions of MH. The molal aqueous solutions of MH were prepared by using Shimadzu electronic balance (Model No. D432613208, Japan) with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1 \text{ mg}$. The solutions were prepared by weight method and the conversion of molality into molarity were done with the help of standard expression (1)²⁷.

$$C = \frac{1000mp}{1000 + mM} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the density of solution, m is the molality of solution and M is the molecular mass of MH. The densities (ρ) and ultrasonic velocities (u) of the solutions was measured with the help of a vibrating-tube

density meter (DSA 5000, Anton Parr, Austria). The DSA was calibrated at the experimental temperatures with triply distilled water and dry air at atmospheric pressure as directed in user manual. The density and sound velocity measurements were accurate to $5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and 0.5 ms^{-1} , respectively. Pure water is not a good conductor of electricity. Ordinary water generally has a specific conductivity of about $3.5 \times 10^{-3} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Most of this conductivity is due to impurities and very little of it is, due to ionization of water. Elaborate precautions are required in order to produce water of conductivity less than $10^{-4} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ by distillation. A small quantity of sodium hydroxide and potassium permanganate were added to water and it was boiled in a large round bottom flask of capacity about five litres. A long fractionating column was attached to the round bottom flask. The steam was condensed through a water condenser and was collected in a flask containing $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ and again it was boiled in a round bottom flask of similar capacity. The collected steam was condensed through a water condenser and was collected in a flask having a guard tube of soda lime in order to avoid the entry of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. The distillation was repeated 3–4 times successively with sodium hydroxide with potassium permanganate and with potassium dichromate till the specific conductance of water was of the order of $10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. For the determination of electrical conductance, conductivity cell has been used. The cell consists of two electrodes of platinum fused in pyrex glass. Connection to the electrode is made through mercury. To determine the cell constant of the conductivity cell the following procedure is used. The cell used for the conductivity measurements is not of accurately known dimensions, and consequently it needs to be calibrated before it is possible to reduce values of specific conductance from measure-

ment of cell resistance. This is done by means of accurately known specific conductance. Suppose a given cell, when filled with a solution of known specific conductance, K is found to have a resistance R , then the cell constant is equal to KR . The cell constant may therefore be thought of as the resistance that the cell would exhibit when filled with liquid of unit conductivity. In the present study, the conductivity cell was calibrated with the solution of potassium chloride in conductivity water. The potassium chloride of AnalaR grade was dried over P_2O_5 in a vacuum desiccator for 24 h.

The conductivity cell before each reading was washed thoroughly with distilled water and then was rinsed four times with 10 ml of the sample solution under study. Solutions of Metformin hydrochloride in water and in 2, 4 and 6% aqueous solution of glucose was made by weight. After filling the solution, the cell was suitably placed inside the water thermostat where it was allowed to attain a constant temperature before conductance measurements were made. Conductance measurements were carried out with a calibrated Digital Conductivity Meter (Elico CM 183EC-TDS Analyser) at 50 Hz. The measured conductance remained stationary with time. The cell

was removed from the water thermostat and the conductance was determined once again.

Results and discussion

The density (ρ), ultrasonic velocity (u) and conductance values measured for different concentrations (0.001–0.01 mol kg⁻¹) of Metformin hydrochloride in 2%, 4% and 6% aqueous glucose (used as a solvent) at 305.15, 310.15 and 315.15 K temperatures have been used to calculate various important parameters such as apparent molar volume, adiabatic compressibility, intermolecular free length specific acoustic impedance and Walden's product etc.

The apparent molar volume²⁸ (reported in Table 2) was obtained by using experimental data according to the eq. (2),

$$\Phi_v = (M/\rho) + (1000(\rho_0 - \rho)/m\rho\rho_0) \quad (2)$$

where Φ_v , m , ρ , ρ_0 and M are the apparent molar volume, molality, density of the solution, density of pure solvent and molar mass of MH, respectively.

The apparent molar volume (Φ_v) of a solute is defined as the difference between the volume of the solution and the volume of the pure solvent per mole of solute^{29–31}. Table 2 shows that the apparent mo-

Table 2. Densities (ρ) and apparent molar volume (Φ_v) of MH in water and in aqueous glucose system at different temperatures

m^a (mol kg ⁻¹)	C (mol L ⁻¹)	Density ρ (g cm ⁻³)			Φ_v (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)		
		305.15 K	310.15 K	315.15 K	305.15 K	310.15 K	315.15 K
Metformin hydrochloride in water							
0.000	0.000000	0.994988	0.993380	0.991483	–	–	–
0.001	0.031543	0.995132	0.993380	0.991537	114.8	117.2	119.7
0.002	0.044606	0.995180	0.993435	0.991582	116.8	119.2	121.2
0.003	0.054628	0.995225	0.993481	0.991625	118.4	120.5	122.3
0.004	0.063075	0.995268	0.993525	0.991665	119.7	121.6	123.6
0.005	0.070515	0.995310	0.993567	0.991703	120.7	122.7	124.7
0.006	0.077241	0.995350	0.993607	0.99174	121.7	123.8	125.7
0.007	0.083425	0.995388	0.993645	0.991776	122.7	124.7	126.6
0.008	0.089179	0.995425	0.993682	0.99181	123.6	125.5	127.4
0.009	0.094582	0.995462	0.993718	0.991842	124.5	126.3	128.3
0.010	0.099692	0.995495	0.993752	0.991875	125.2	127.2	128.9
Metformin hydrochloride in 2% glucose							
0.000	0.000000	0.995652	0.994072	0.992212	–	–	–
0.001	0.031669	1.003069	0.999944	0.998701	115.7	118.5	120.8
0.002	0.044784	1.003114	0.999987	0.998742	117.7	120.5	122.8

Table-2 (contd.)

0.003	0.054845	1.003156	1.000028	0.99878	119.3	121.3	124.4
0.004	0.063326	1.003195	1.000065	0.998814	120.9	123.5	126.3
0.005	0.070796	1.003233	1.0001	0.998848	122.1	124.9	127.4
0.006	0.077548	1.003268	1.000132	0.998878	123.4	126.3	128.8
0.007	0.083755	1.003301	1.000162	0.998906	124.6	127.6	130.2
0.008	0.089532	1.003331	1.000192	0.998933	125.8	128.6	131.1
0.009	0.094957	1.003356	1.00022	0.998956	127.3	129.6	132.4
0.010	0.10009	1.003453	1.00024	0.998976	128.3	131.2	133.7
Metformin hydrochloride in 4% glucose							
0.000	0.000000	0.996346	0.994786	0.992956	–	–	–
0.001	0.031788	1.010652	1.008885	1.006921	116.7	119.2	121.7
0.002	0.044952	1.010694	1.008925	1.006959	118.8	121.3	123.8
0.003	0.055052	1.010733	1.008962	1.006993	120.5	122.9	125.8
0.004	0.063564	1.010769	1.008995	1.007025	122.1	124.8	127.3
0.005	0.071062	1.010803	1.009026	1.007053	123.5	126.3	129.1
0.006	0.07784	1.010835	1.009056	1.007081	124.7	127.5	130.2
0.007	0.084071	1.010866	1.009082	1.007105	125.8	129.2	131.6
0.008	0.089869	1.010895	1.00911	1.007128	126.8	129.8	132.8
0.009	0.095314	1.010921	1.009135	1.007149	128.1	130.7	133.9
0.010	0.100463	1.010945	1.009155	1.007169	129.1	132.2	134.9
Metformin hydrochloride in 6% glucose							
0.000	0.000000	0.997014	0.995494	0.993704	–	–	–
0.001	0.031804	1.011632	1.009922	1.005403	116.8	120.0	123.1
0.002	0.044974	1.011672	1.00996	1.005439	119.4	122.5	125.7
0.003	0.055078	1.01171	1.009995	1.005472	121.3	124.4	127.5
0.004	0.063595	1.011745	1.010027	1.005501	122.9	126.1	129.4
0.005	0.071096	1.011777	1.010056	1.005529	124.5	127.7	130.8
0.006	0.077877	1.011807	1.010083	1.005555	125.9	129.1	132.0
0.007	0.084111	1.011836	1.010108	1.005578	127.0	130.5	133.4
0.008	0.089912	1.011863	1.010132	1.005598	128.1	131.6	134.7
0.009	0.095359	1.011886	1.010155	1.00562	129.4	132.5	135.6
0.010	0.100511	1.011909	1.010175	1.005638	130.5	133.6	136.7

^a*m* is the molality of MH in aqueous glucose solutions. The standard uncertainty in molality as per stated purities is $u(m) = \pm 0.1$ mg. Standard uncertainties in $u(\rho)$ density measurements are $\pm 5 \times 10^{-6}$ g cm⁻³. Standard uncertainties in $u(T)$ temperatures are $\pm 1 \times 10^{-2}$. Standard uncertainties in $u(P)$ pressures are 0.1 MPa.

lar volume of MH increases with increase in temperature and with concentration of glucose in water-glucose system.

The apparent molar volume occupied by one mole of a solute at infinite dilution is called partial molar volume of a solute in solution³². The partial molar volume also called limiting apparent molar volume is calculated by least square fitting of Φ_v vs \sqrt{c} by the Masson's eq. (3)³³,

$$\Phi_v = \Phi_v^0 + S_v \sqrt{c} \quad (3)$$

The intercept gives partial molar volume (Φ_v^0) which signifies solute-solvent interactions independent of solute-solute interactions and the slope S_v called Masson's coefficient is a measure of solute-solute interactions³⁴. The values of Φ_v^0 and S_v along with standard deviations for MH in different aqueous glucose solutions at the experimental temperatures are reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Partial molar volume (Φ_V^0), Masson's coefficient (S_V), partial molar expansibility (Φ_E^0), isobaric thermal expansion coefficient (α°), a , b , c and Hepler's constant values for MH in water and water-glucose system

Solvent	Φ_V^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)			S_V		
	305.15 K	310.15 K	315.15 K	305.15 K	310.15 K	315.15 K
Water	110.1	112.7	115.0	150.9	143.9	139.1
2%	109.4	112.1	114.4	184.2	185.2	188.7
4%	110.7	112.9	115.1	179.9	188.5	195.3
6%	110.9	113.5	116.7	198.4	198.6	200.4
Solvent	Φ_E^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)			α° (K ⁻¹)		
	305.15 K	310.15 K	315.15 K	305.15 K	310.15 K	315.15 K
Water	0.622	0.544	0.464	0.005649	0.004826	0.004034
2%	0.608	0.508	0.408	0.005557	0.004531	0.003575
4%	0.395	0.564	0.757	0.003568	0.004995	0.006576
6%	0.463	0.583	0.703	0.004174	0.005136	0.006023
Solvent	a	b	c	$\left(\frac{\partial^2 \Phi_V^0}{\partial T^2}\right)_P = 2c$		
	305.15 K	310.15 K	315.15 K	305.15 K	310.15 K	315.15 K
Water	826.61	-5.504	0.008	0.016		
2%	4809.57	-6.71	0.010	0.021		
4%	5263.26	-10.64	0.018	0.036		
6%	4263.08	-6.86	0.012	0.024		

The trend from the Table 3 indicates that Φ_V^0 values are positive, which signifies that there exist strong solute solvent interactions for MH in water- glucose system. The value of Φ_V^0 increases with rise in temperature that may be due to decrease in hydrogen bonding in water-glucose system with rise in temperature and thus free molecules of water will be available for the solvation of MH. These trends are in conformity with the values obtained for apparent molar volume as listed in Table 2. The plots showing the variation of partial molar volume concentration for Metformin hydrochloride in water and water-glucose system at different temperatures are given in Fig. 3(a-d).

The value of Masson's coefficient, S_V is positive for MH in water and water-glucose system suggests that there are strong solute-solute interactions which are due to electrostatic force of attraction between drug molecules.

The temperature dependence³⁵ of Φ_V^0 is given by the following eq. (4),

$$\Phi_V^0 = a + bT + cT^2 \quad (4)$$

where a , b and c are constants for a given system

and T is temperature expressed in Kelvin. The values of constants a , b and c are calculated by using eq. (4) at different temperatures and are given in Table 3.

The values of partial molar volume expansibility (Φ_E^0), of MH was obtained from the temperature dependence of partial molar volume³⁶, Φ_V^0 given by eq. (5),

$$\Phi_E^0 = [\partial \Phi_V^0 / \partial T] = b + 2cT \quad (5)$$

The importance of Φ_E^0 lies in the fact that it helps in the elucidation of the long range structure making or structure breaking effects of solutes³⁷⁻³⁹. The values of Φ_E^0 and α° obtained for MH in different water-glucose system at different temperatures are recorded in Table 3. The value of Φ_E^0 for MH in water and water-glucose system increases with increase in temperature indicates that caging effect is present. The isobaric thermal expansion coefficient (α°) for MH in water and water-glucose system is obtained from the values of Φ_E^0 and Φ_V^0 using the following eq. (6),

$$\alpha^\circ = \Phi_E^0 / \Phi_V^0 \quad (6)$$

The α° value increases with increase in concentra-

(a) MH in water

(b) MH in 2% glucose

(c) MH in 4% glucose

(d) MH in 6% glucose

Fig. 3. Plots showing the variation of Φ_V with concentration for Metformin hydrochloride in water and water-glucose system at different temperatures.

tion of glucose in water-glucose system. This may be due to structure making of MH in water and water-glucose system. The plots showing the variation of Φ_E^0 with temperature for MH in water, 2%, 4% and 6% aqueous glucose are shown in Fig. 4(a,b).

Hepler devised a method to account for structure making and breaking capacity of solutes in aqueous solutions on the basis of sign of $(\partial^2\Phi_V^0/\partial T^2)_P$. The Hepler's constant gives the qualitative details on hydration of drugs. The positive value of⁴⁰ $(\partial^2\Phi_V^0/$

$\partial T^2)_P]$ indicates that solute is structure maker and negative value of Hepler's constant indicates structure breaker behaviour of solute. The values of $(\partial^2\Phi_V^0/\partial T^2)_P$ calculated for MH in water and in different ternary solutions are listed in Table 3.

$$(\partial^2\Phi_V^0/\partial T^2)_P = 2c \quad (7)$$

The positive values of $(\partial^2\Phi_V^0/\partial T^2)_P$ for MH in water and water-glucose system suggests that MH acts as a structure maker in water, 2%, 4% and 6% glucose-

Fig. 4. Plots showing the variation of Φ_E^0 with temperature for MH in water, 2%, 4% and 6% aqueous glucose.

water system. The structure making ability of MH is also confirmed by the variation of Φ_E^0 with temperature.

Ultrasonic studies :

The density and ultrasonic velocity data for MH in water and water- glucose system are given in Table 4 have been used to calculate acoustical parameters like adiabatic compressibility (β), intermolecular free length (L_f) and specific acoustic impedance (Z) which are useful in elucidating the nature of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions occurring in the solutions.

The Adiabatic compressibility (β) was obtained

by applying Newton-Laplace eq. (8)⁴¹, defined as

$$\beta = \left(-\frac{1}{v} \right) \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial P} \right)_S$$

or

$$\beta = 1/u^2 \rho \quad (8)$$

where u is the ultrasonic velocity and ρ is the density of solution. The data (Table 4) shows that adiabatic compressibility values for MH in water and water-glucose system decreases with increase in concentration of MH at different temperatures. This may be due to strong electric field (electrostriction), the solvent molecules within the primary solvation shell of electrolytic solution become incompressible moreover increasing concentration of ions results in more solvent molecules to engage in incompressible solvation spheres thereby decreasing the adiabatic compressibility⁴². This decrease in adiabatic compressibility with increase in concentration of MH in water and water-glucose system shows the predominance of drug solvent interactions in water-glucose systems. As the temperature increases, the attractive forces among solvent molecules decreases and thus there are more free solvent molecules available for solvation of drug molecules which is confirmed by the decreasing β values with increase in temperature.

The plots for the variation of β and L_f with concentration of MH in these systems are shown in Fig. 5.

According to Jacobson's intermolecular free length theory for liquids⁴³, the molecules of liquid are assumed to be spherical and the average value of the distance that the ultrasonic waves travel between the two molecules is called the intermolecular free length.

The experimental values of ultrasonic velocity u are related to L_f ⁴⁴ as

$$L_f = \frac{K}{U_{\text{exp}} \sqrt{\rho_{\text{exp}}}} = K \sqrt{\beta} \quad (9)$$

where K is the temperature dependent constant ($= (93.875 + 0.375T) \times 10^{-8}$)⁴⁵.

The values for intermolecular free length show

Table 4. Ultrasonic velocity (u), adiabatic compressibility (β), intermolecular free length (L_f) and specific acoustic impedance (Z) values for MH in water and water-glucose system at different temperatures and atmospheric pressure

m^t	Ultrasonic velocity (u) ($m\ s^{-1}$)				β ($10^{-10}\ Pa^{-1}$)				L_f ($10^{-11}\ m$)				Z ($10^6\ kg\ m^{-2}\ s^{-1}$)			
	305.15K	310.15K	315.15K	315.15K	305.15K	310.15K	315.15K	315.15K	305.15K	310.15K	315.15K	315.15K	305.15K	310.15K	315.15K	315.15K
	Metformin hydrochloride in water															
0.001	1513.84	1523.75	1532.13	1532.13	4.3848	4.3354	4.2963	4.2963	4.359345	4.376306	4.398017	1.50647	1.50647	1.50647	1.51916	
0.002	1513.98	1523.95	1532.38	1532.38	4.3838	4.3341	4.2947	4.2947	4.358837	4.375659	4.3972	1.50668	1.50668	1.50668	1.51949	
0.003	1514.12	1524.14	1532.64	1532.64	4.3828	4.3328	4.2931	4.2931	4.358336	4.375074	4.396359	1.50689	1.50689	1.50689	1.51980	
0.004	1514.19	1524.21	1532.70	1532.70	4.3822	4.3322	4.2926	4.2926	4.35804	4.374723	4.396098	1.50702	1.50702	1.50702	1.51992	
0.005	1514.26	1524.27	1532.76	1532.76	4.3816	4.3317	4.2921	4.2921	4.357747	4.374463	4.395841	1.50715	1.50715	1.50715	1.52004	
0.006	1514.36	1524.34	1532.82	1532.82	4.3809	4.3311	4.2915	4.2915	4.357371	4.374178	4.395588	1.50731	1.50731	1.50731	1.52016	
0.007	1514.41	1524.4	1532.88	1532.88	4.3800	4.3306	4.2910	4.2910	4.357144	4.373925	4.395336	1.50742	1.50742	1.50742	1.52028	
0.008	1514.59	1524.59	1533.03	1533.03	4.3792	4.3294	4.2900	4.2900	4.356747	4.373301	4.39483	1.50766	1.50766	1.50766	1.52048	
0.009	1514.71	1524.71	1533.44	1533.44	4.3783	4.3285	4.2876	4.2876	4.356119	4.372882	4.394444	1.50784	1.50784	1.50784	1.52094	
0.010	1514.82	1524.83	1533.25	1533.25	4.3775	4.3277	4.2885	4.2885	4.355731	4.372493	4.394056	1.50801	1.50801	1.50801	1.52080	
	Metformin hydrochloride in 2% glucose															
0.001	1521.06	1531.08	1541.08	1541.08	4.3094	4.2660	4.2161	4.2161	4.321454	4.341185	4.356764	1.52572	1.52572	1.52572	1.53907	
0.002	1521.12	1531.15	1541.15	1541.15	4.3087	4.2655	4.2155	4.2155	4.321186	4.340893	4.356477	1.52585	1.52585	1.52585	1.53921	
0.003	1521.18	1531.2	1541.21	1541.21	4.3082	4.2650	4.2150	4.2150	4.320925	4.340662	4.356225	1.52598	1.52598	1.52598	1.53933	
0.004	1521.24	1531.26	1541.28	1541.28	4.3079	4.2645	4.2145	4.2145	4.320671	4.340412	4.355953	1.52615	1.52615	1.52615	1.53945	
0.005	1521.29	1531.32	1541.32	1541.32	4.3076	4.2640	4.2141	4.2141	4.320447	4.340166	4.355765	1.52620	1.52620	1.52620	1.53954	
0.006	1521.35	1531.36	1541.38	1541.38	4.3073	4.2637	4.2137	4.2137	4.320201	4.339983	4.355531	1.52632	1.52632	1.52632	1.53965	
0.007	1521.42	1531.42	1541.44	1541.44	4.3071	4.2632	4.2132	4.2132	4.319932	4.339748	4.3553	1.52644	1.52644	1.52644	1.53975	
0.008	1521.48	1531.48	1541.5	1541.5	4.3069	4.2627	4.2128	4.2128	4.319697	4.339513	4.355072	1.52654	1.52654	1.52654	1.53985	
0.009	1521.54	1531.54	1541.56	1541.56	4.3067	4.2623	4.2124	4.2124	4.319472	4.339282	4.354852	1.52664	1.52664	1.52664	1.53995	
0.010	1521.58	1531.59	1541.62	1541.62	4.3065	4.2619	4.2120	4.2120	4.31915	4.339097	4.354639	1.52683	1.52683	1.52683	1.54004	
	Metformin hydrochloride in 4% glucose															
0.001	1527.82	1537.24	1547.02	1547.02	4.2389	4.1944	4.1496	4.1496	4.286162	4.304587	4.322285	1.54409	1.54409	1.54409	1.55772	
0.002	1527.89	1537.28	1547.06	1547.06	4.2383	4.1940	4.1492	4.1492	4.285877	4.304389	4.322091	1.54422	1.54422	1.54422	1.55782	
0.003	1527.96	1537.32	1547.12	1547.12	4.2377	4.1936	4.1488	4.1488	4.285598	4.304198	4.321851	1.54434	1.54434	1.54434	1.55793	
0.004	1527.98	1537.36	1547.16	1547.16	4.2374	4.1933	4.1484	4.1484	4.285465	4.304016	4.32167	1.54443	1.54443	1.54443	1.55802	
0.005	1528.02	1537.41	1547.21	1547.21	4.2371	4.1929	4.1480	4.1480	4.285281	4.30381	4.321471	1.54452	1.54452	1.54452	1.55812	
0.006	1528.08	1537.46	1547.26	1547.26	4.2366	4.1925	4.1477	4.1477	4.285045	4.303606	4.321271	1.54463	1.54463	1.54463	1.55821	
0.007	1528.14	1537.52	1547.32	1547.32	4.2362	4.1921	4.1472	4.1472	4.284811	4.303383	4.321052	1.54474	1.54474	1.54474	1.55831	
0.008	1528.2	1537.56	1547.37	1547.37	4.2357	4.1917	4.1469	4.1469	4.284581	4.303211	4.320863	1.54485	1.54485	1.54485	1.55842	

Table-4 (contd.)

0.009	1528.26	1537.61	1547.42	4.2355	4.1913	4.1465	4.284358	4.303018	4.320678	1.54191	1.55165	1.55848
0.010	1528.32	1537.66	1547.46	4.2349	4.1910	4.1462	4.284139	4.302835	4.320524	1.54201	1.55173	1.55855
							Metformin hydrochloride in 6% glucose					
0.001	1535.04	1545.02	1555.02	4.1950	4.1480	4.1132	4.263936	4.280711	4.303293	1.55289	1.56035	1.56342
0.002	1535.09	1545.08	1555.08	4.1946	4.1475	4.1124	4.263712	4.280465	4.30305	1.55300	1.56046	1.56353
0.003	1535.16	1545.14	1555.12	4.1940	4.1471	4.1124	4.263438	4.280224	4.302869	1.55313	1.56058	1.5636
0.004	1535.20	1545.19	1555.18	4.1937	4.1467	4.1120	4.263253	4.280018	4.302641	1.55323	1.56068	1.56373
0.005	1535.26	1545.24	1555.24	4.1932	4.1463	4.1115	4.263019	4.279818	4.302415	1.55334	1.56077	1.56383
0.006	1535.30	1545.30	1555.28	4.1929	4.1458	4.1112	4.262845	4.279595	4.302249	1.55342	1.56088	1.5639
0.007	1535.36	1545.36	1555.32	4.1924	4.1454	4.1109	4.262617	4.279376	4.302089	1.55353	1.56098	1.56399
0.008	1535.42	1545.42	1555.36	4.1920	4.1450	4.1106	4.262394	4.279159	4.301935	1.55363	1.56107	1.56406
0.009	1535.46	1545.48	1555.42	4.1917	4.1446	4.1102	4.262234	4.278944	4.301722	1.55371	1.56117	1.56416
0.010	1535.52	1545.54	1555.48	4.1905	4.1442	4.1098	4.262019	4.278735	4.301518	1.55482	1.56126	1.5642

⁴m is the molality of MH in aqueous glucose solutions. The standard uncertainty in molality as per stated purities is $u(m) = \pm 0.1$ mg. Standard uncertainties in $u(u)$ ultrasonic velocity measurements are ± 0.5 m s⁻¹. Standard uncertainties in $u(T)$ temperatures are $\pm 1 \times 10^{-2}$. Standard uncertainties in $u(P)$ pressures are 0.1 MPa.

Fig. 5. Plots for (a) the variation of β and (b) the L_f for MH in 2% aqueous glucose at different temperature.

similar behaviour to that of adiabatic compressibility. Table 4 shows that L_f values decreases with temperature as well as with increasing MH concentration in different systems. These trends show the presence of drug solvent interactions in these systems.

Specific acoustic impedance which is a measure of the resistance offered by the medium for the propa-

gation of sound waves through it. The values of Z for MH in water and in different water-glucose systems are reported in Table 4 by using eq. (8). The values of Z are compatible with the values of β and L_f indicating the presence of drug solvent interactions in the studied systems^{46,47}.

$$Z = up \tag{10}$$

where u and ρ are the ultrasonic velocity and densities of solution respectively.

Conductance study :

In the present investigation, the specific conductance, molar conductance and Walden product for Metformin hydrochloride in water and in glucose at

305.15 K, 310.15 K and 315.15 K temperatures have been determined. Electrical conductance is an important parameter to understand degree of dissociation, nature of solute-solvent interactions, ion-association and dissociation constant and above all the structure making/breaking tendency. The measurement of conductance as a function of concentration gives the conductance at infinite dilution Λ_m^0 . The limiting molar conductance is evaluated by using Kraus-Bray conductivity equation^{48,49}. The structural effects of ions on the solvents in aqueous solutions are derived by comparison of their Walden product at different temperatures^{50,51}. Greater the Walden product of the electrolyte in a given solvent, greater

Fig. 6. Plots for variation of specific conductance with concentration for Metformin hydrochloride in water and water-glucose system at different temperatures.

Table 5. Molar conductance (Λ_m) of Metformin hydrochloride in water and aqueous glucose at different temperatures

Concentration ($C^{1/2}$) (mol/L)	Λ_m ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)		
	305.15 K	310.15 K	315.15 K
	Water		
0.031623	119.01	175.00	210.01
0.044721	105.00	132.51	160.00
0.054772	95.04	111.66	135.12
0.063246	87.50	98.75	121.25
0.070711	81.02	91.00	112.21
0.077460	75.81	84.16	104.16
0.083666	77.10	86.42	99.28
0.089443	73.75	86.50	95.25
0.094868	74.66	84.55	93.11
0.100000	72.01	83.10	91.50
	2% Aqueous glucose		
0.031623	102.02	125.25	121.56
0.044721	90.5.12	105.04	109.52
0.054772	85.00	93.33	101.66
0.063246	78.25	86.54	94.75
0.070711	74.41	81.25	90.36
0.077460	70.66	75.83	85.83
0.083666	69.42	76.42	83.57
0.089443	67.15	74.37	81.87
0.094868	65.66	73.55	80.55
0.100000	65.67	74.12	81.58
	4% Aqueous glucose		
0.031623	100.25	105.59	120.24
0.044721	89.51	94.24	106.25
0.054772	83.25	86.66	96.66
0.063246	78.25	82.51	90.14
0.070711	74.24	78.25	86.17
0.077460	70.83	75.83	82.51
0.083666	70.57	77.14	82.14
0.089443	70.25	75.62	80.62
0.094868	69.11	73.84	78.88
0.100000	67.55	73.53	78.51
	6% Aqueous glucose		
0.031623	90.24	100.27	112.01
0.044721	82.52	90.24	99.53
0.054772	76.62	83.33	91.67
0.063246	72.57	78.75	86.25
0.070711	70.36	75.36	83.35
0.077460	67.55	72.89	79.76
0.083666	66.42	72.57	79.28
0.089443	65.62	72.35	78.12
0.094868	66.41	72.22	77.77
0.100000	66.24	72.15	77.58

is its solute-solvent interactions. Structure maker/breaker behaviour of an electrolyte is determined by plotting Walden product versus temperature. Negative temperature coefficient suggests that electrolyte behaves as a structure breaker and the positive coefficient accounts for the structure making behaviour of the electrolyte⁵². The viscosity of electrolyte is usually studied to obtain information on ion-solvent interactions^{53,54}.

The values of specific conductance (κ) for Metformin hydrochloride in water and water-glucose system increases with increase in concentrations. The value also increases with increase in the temperature. This may be due to increase in concentration of Metformin hydrochloride (0.001–0.01 *m*) in water and water-glucose system. The values of specific conductance also increases with rise in the temperature in water and water-glucose system which may be due to increase in ionic conductance of the solute with rise in temperature.

The plots of variation of specific conductance with concentration and with temperature for Metformin hydrochloride in water and water-glucose system are given in Fig. 7.

The molar conductance for Metformin hydrochloride in water and water-glucose system is calculated by the below given equation :

$$\Lambda_m = \frac{\kappa \times 1000}{C} \quad (11)$$

Here κ is specific conductance and C is molar concentration. The molar conductance for Metformin hydrochloride in water and in glucose at 305.15 K, 310.15 K and 315.15 K temperatures have been recorded in Table 5.

The values of molar conductance shows a decrease with increase in concentration of glucose and the molar conductance values are greater at higher temperature. The decrease in the value of molar conductance with increase in the concentration of glucose may be due to increase in solute-solvent interactions, thereby decreasing the ionic mobility. The higher values of molar conductance at higher temperature may be due to the greater mobility of ions at higher

Fig. 7. Plots for the variation of molar conductance with water and different concentration of glucose.

temperature due to which interionic effects are decreased and the values of molar conductance increased. The plots for the variation of molar conductance in water and different concentration of glucose are shown in Fig. 7.

The limiting molar conductance has been obtained from the intercept by applying the least squares fit to the experimental values of $1/\lambda_m$ vs $\lambda_m C$ by using Kraus-Bray conductivity equation which is another form of Ostwald's dilution law⁵⁵ :

$$1/\lambda_m = 1/\lambda_m^0 + \lambda_m C/K_c \lambda_m^{02}$$

here λ_m^0 is the limiting molar conductance, K_c is dissociation constant and C is molar concentration.

The limiting molar conductance (Λ_m^0), signifies solute-solvent interactions⁵⁶. In the present study, linear plots of $1/\lambda_m$ versus $\lambda_m C$ have been obtained for Metformin hydrochloride (0.001–0.01 *m*) in water and in aqueous solution of glucose at 305.15, 310.15, and 315.15 K temperatures. The values of limiting molar conductance decreases with increase in the concentration of glucose which is attributed to greater interionic or solute-solvent interactions at higher concentration and these interactions decreases at higher temperature due to greater kinetic energy of species at higher temperature. The sample plot for the variation of $1/\lambda_m$ vs $\lambda_m C$ for MH in 2% glucose is shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. The sample plot of $1/\lambda_m$ vs $\lambda_m C$ for Metformin hydrochloride in 2% aqueous glucose solution at 305.15 K.

The values of limiting molar conductance for Metformin hydrochloride in water, 2%, 4% and 6% aqueous glucose at three different temperature (305.15 K, 310.15 K, 315.15 K) have been recorded in Table 6.

Table 6. Limiting molar conductance at different temperature for MH in water and 2%, 4% and 6% aqueous glucose

Solvent	Λ_m^0 ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)		
	305.15 K	310.15 K	315.15 K
Water	151.74	218.34	456.62
2% Glucose	117.65	160.77	191.20
4% Glucose	111.73	116.14	137.74
6% Glucose	98.23	110.86	125.16

Walden product is the product of limiting molar conductance and the viscosity of the solvent system. Larger the viscosity of the medium, the lesser is the mobility and hence lesser is the conductance of the ion. The values of viscosity and hence the values of Walden product increases with increase in the concentration of glucose. Greater values of Walden product at higher concentrations signifies greater solute-solvent interactions. Structure maker/breaker behaviour⁵⁷ of Metformin hydrochloride in glucose is determined by plotting Walden product with tem-

perature. The positive temperature coefficient suggests that Metformin hydrochloride behaves as a structure maker in glucose.

The values of Walden product, viscosity and limiting molar conductance for Metformin hydrochloride in water and in glucose at 305.15 K, 310.15 K and 315.15 K temperatures have been recorded in Table 7.

Table 7. Viscosity and Walden product for water and 2%, 4% and 6% aqueous solutions of glucose

Solvent	λ_m^0 ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	η_0 (cP)	$\lambda_m^0 \eta_0$ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cP}$)
Water			
(305.15 K)	151.74	0.7679	116.5
310.15 K	218.34	0.7089	154.7
315.15 K	456.62	0.6272	286.3
2% Glucose			
(305.15 K)	117.6 1	0.7942	93.3
310.15 K	160.77	0.7712	123.9
315.15 K	191.20	0.7536	144.1
4% Glucose			
(305.15 K)	111.73	0.8206	91.6
310.15 K	116.14	0.8116	94.2
315.15 K	137.74	0.7962	109.6
6% Glucose			
(305.15 K)	98.231	0.8432	82.8
310.15 K	110.86	0.8356	92.6
315.15 K	125.16	0.8212	102.7

The Walden product data for Metformin hydrochloride (0.001–0.01 *m*) in water and in aqueous solutions of 2%, 4% and 6% glucose at three different temperature (305.15 K, 310.15 K, 315.15 K) is recorded in Table 7. The temperature coefficient of

Walden product i.e. $\left(\frac{d(\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0)}{dT}\right)_P$ is positive,

Metformin hydrochloride (0.001–0.01 *m*) in 2%, 4% and 6% glucose at three different temperature (305.15 K, 310.15 K, 315.15 K) behave as structure maker^{58,59} in this solvent. The sample plots showing variation of $\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$ versus temperature for Metformin hydrochloride (0.001–0.01 *m*) in water and in aqueous solutions of glucose at different temperatures (305.15 K, 310.15 K, 315.15 K) are shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Plots of $\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$ vs temperature for Metformin hydrochloride in water and aqueous glucose at different temperatures.

Thus conclusion drawn from conductance studies is that Metformin hydrochloride (0.001–0.01 *m*) behave as structure maker in 2%, 4% and 6% aqueous glucose at temperatures 305.15 K, 310.15 K and 315.15 K.

Conclusion

The partial molar volume, partial molar expansibility, adiabatic compressibility, intermolecular free length and specific acoustic impedance values for MH in water and water-glucose system indicate the presence of strong solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions and the interactions are strength-

ened with increase in concentration of glucose. The increase in the value of Φ_E^0 with temperature and positive value of Hepler's constant for MH in water and water-glucose system indicates that MH behaves as a structure maker in water and aqueous glucose system. Also the conclusion drawn from conductance studies is that Metformin hydrochloride (0.001–0.01 *m*) behave as structure maker in 2%, 4% and 6% aqueous glucose at temperatures 305.15 K, 310.15 K and 315.15 K. Since MH behaves as structure maker hence it is safer for the patient suffering from hypertension also.

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